

THE VERBALIZATIONS OF THE CONCEPT ‘HAPPINESS’ IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: This thesis aims to give brief information about semantic fields in linguistic perspective and analyzes semantic field members of the concept ‘happiness’ in English. In this paper, the concept verbalizers have been categorized into noun, adjective and verb groups in lexical level and other linguistic units expressed by stylistic devices and figures of speech have been provided as examples in syntactic level.

Key words: Field Theory, semantic field, concept, concept verbalization, lexical level, syntactic level, personification, metaphor.

Semantic Field is a term used to describe a group of words, all of which share a similar concept, theme or subject¹. The various feelings, emotions, thoughts or ideas which a specific word invokes can be connotations. In linguistics, a semantic field is a lexical set of words grouped semantically (by meaning) that refers to a specific subject². While the initial views on the semantic field theory go back to the ideas of the German linguist W. Humboldt from the middle of the 19th century, the linguists who put forward this idea in the real sense were the German and Swiss structural linguists of the 1930s, such as Ipsen, Jolls, Porzig and Trier³.

Pablo Navarro says that today, dividing the words in the dictionary into groups and combining them in different lexical fields is one of the effective methods proved in teaching and learning foreign languages. Because the lexical field causes students to increase their vocabulary and easy memorization of words, and develops lexical

¹ <https://interpreture.com/semantic-field-explained/>

² Howard Jackson, Etienne Zé Amvela, *Words, Meaning, and Vocabulary*, Continuum, 2000, p14

³ Gao Ch, Xu B. The application of semantic field theory to English vocabulary learning. – *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, Vol 3, Academy Publisher Manufactured in Finland. 2013. – P. 2030.

competences such as the ability to use words and concepts in the foreign language being studied⁴.

In order to study the semantic field of the concept ‘happiness’, it is appropriate to separate the field members or the lexical verbalizers of ‘happiness’ into groups. They have been divided into nouns, adjectives, adverbs, and verbs in the lexical level. 35 lexemes in the noun category have been collected through dictionaries. Among the noun group lexemes the following 25 nouns are considered as active synonyms for the word ‘happiness’: *pleasure, joy, delight, contentment, ecstasy, euphoria, elation, welfare, well-being, bliss, uplift, job satisfaction, glee, radiance, jubilation, afterglow, festivity, buoyancy, delirium, high, harmony, fulfillment, the feel-good factor*⁵. While next 4 lexemes such as *jollity, bonhomie, exaltation, felicity* are often used in formal style, literal style uses *vivacity, rapture, cheer and transports of joy* as happiness synonyms. *Nirvana* is also one of the synonyms of happiness which has a religious character (Buddhism) and mostly used in oral speech. They are considered lexical paradigms connected on the basis of semantic connection, and in their turn form a whole microsystem.

Next, it is important to consider the verbalizers of the concept of happiness, which is related to the adjective word group. Total 67 adjectives have been separated and the following 44 of them are distinguished as active synonyms for the lexeme ‘happy’: *glad, alive, pleased, content, satisfied, contented, cheerful, carefree, exuberant, bouncy, bright, bubbly, buoyant, cheery, chirpy, cock-a-hoop, delighted, delirious, ecstatic, elated, euphoric, excited, exhilarated, exuberant, flattered, fulfilled, giddy, gleeful, good, high, jolly, jovial, joyful, jubilant, light-hearted, overjoyed, relieved, satisfied, sunny, thrilled, touched, triumphant, uplifted*. 4 of them belong to old fashioned words in the English dictionary: *careless, chipper, gay, merry*. According to the stylistic aspect, there are 6 words suitable for

⁴ Navarro P.M. The lexical field, a key to semantics. – CAUCE, Revistade Filología y su Didáctica, N° 22-23, 1999-2000. – P. 539-548.

⁵ <https://www.macmillandictionary.com/thesaurus-category/british/feeling-happy>

literature style (*enraptured, blithe, intoxicated, jocund, seraphic, upbeat*), and 6 words suitable for informal oral style (*blissed out, perky, Stoked, tickled, upbeat*), and those of a formal style are only 3 (*ebullient, exalted, exultant*). Interestingly, there are also adjectives that are specific to only a certain version of the English language, such as *chuffed, rumbustious* which were determined as specific to the British English, and *rumbunctious* to the American English, and finally, *rapt* to the Australian English.

In lexicographic sources, it was found that lexical units of 17 verbs are used in the representation of the concept of happiness: *Please, excite, hearten, uplift, fulfill, boost, pacify, buoy, elate, exhilarate, fortify, gladden, gratify, lift, mollify, stroke, tickle*⁶. However, a great number of verbs can be used to verbalize the concept ‘happiness’ in metaphorical way. For example: *Leap up for joy, burst with, feel like her feet barely touched the ground, Inside, jumped for joy, shout for joy, savored the feeling of contentment, heart almost broke with joy*⁷.

In the process of verbalization, different stylistic devices and figures of speeches can be used. One of them is personification which, according to the Oxford Learner’s Dictionary, is defined as “the practice of representing objects, qualities, etc. as humans, in art and literature; an object, quality, etc. that is represented in this way.” The Cambridge Dictionary defines personification as “the act of giving a human quality or characteristic to something which is not human. In the following examples, personification is used to describe happiness: *happiness danced through her thoughts, happiness overtook me, happiness streaked through him, contentment filled her heart, joy rushed through me, her heart was singing, happiness crept over him, her happiness grew*.

Expressions with ‘to be’ is also active in English to help verbalizing the concept ‘happiness’. Here are common expressions with auxiliary verb ‘to be’: *to be paralyzed with happiness, to be flabbergasted with joy, to be intoxicated with joy,*

⁶ <https://www.macmillandictionary.com/thesaurus-category/british/to-make-someone-happy-or-happier>

⁷ [How to Describe Happiness: 100 Phrases | BRYN DONOVAN](#)

to be wild with joy, to be suffused with happiness, to be filled with joyful energy, to be weak with gratitude, to be transported with joy, to be overcome with happiness, to be buzzing with happiness, to be in heaven.

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7. [How to Describe Happiness: 100 Phrases | BRYN DONOVAN](#)